

Adsorptive removal of sodium dodecyl sulfate from aqueous solution using chemically modified over-burnt brick granules

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Manuscript received 15 November 2017, revised 22 February 2018, accepted 22 February 2018

Abstract : Over-burnt bricks, if not recycled or reused, are usually landfilled for disposal. In the present study, three different types of modified brick granules were employed as adsorbent materials for anionic surfactant (AS) removal. The modification of brick granules were done chemically by treatment with 1 N HNO₃, 1 N NaOH and 1% FeCl₃, and the modified materials were designated as BG-3, BG-4 and BG-5, respectively. Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was considered as an AS in our study. Among the three adsorbents, BG-5 was found to be the best, and hence it was selected as our adsorbent for AS removal. The characterization of BG-5 was done by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and pH_{ZPC} analyses. The effects of particle size, solution pH, adsorbent dosage, initial SDS concentration and contact time were studied. The equilibrium time chosen was 6 h. Maximum adsorption occurred under acidic conditions, and the optimum pH for the study was selected as 6.5. Under equilibrium condition using the adsorbent (BG-5) dose of 10 g/L, the SDS removal (at an initial concentration of 100 mg/L), was ~81.5%. The equilibrium studies via non-linear regression method confirmed that, the Freundlich isotherm was the appropriate model for the adsorption process. The adsorption data of SDS on to BG-5 was best corroborated by pseudo-second order kinetic model. Results indicated that, the adsorption was exothermic and spontaneous in nature.

Keywords : Adsorption, anionic surfactant, sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), over-burnt brick.

I. Introduction

The focus of the current research is on removing anionic surfactant (AS), which is the active constituent of detergents utilized in low-income markets. The solubilizing phenomenon of surfactants makes them very useful for domestic and industrial applications. In that regard, the worldwide surfactant production increased exponentially (which is >10 million tons per year), and around 60% of its production is to be accounted for AS. Moreover, these surfactant-based detergents are being used extensively in hospitals as washing and cleaning agent. Their regular application causes the increase in the concentration of the surfactant in the receiving water bodies resulting in the huge foam production, and they also enter into the underground water resources

leading to the groundwater contamination. They not only create health hazards like dermatitis, but also cause short- and long-term effects on the aquatic ecosystem¹. Due to the aforesaid reasons, suitable water treatment is needed that can reduce the surfactant concentration from domestic and industrial effluents. Many public health and environmental protection agencies have fixed the permissible range for AS as 0.5–1.0 mg/L.

The conventional techniques for the sequestration of surfactant molecules from the aqueous solution involve processes such as chemical precipitation, membrane separation, chemical and electro-chemical oxidation, photo-catalytic degradation, adsorption and various biological methods². Among these methods, many are not cost-effective, environment-

friendly, and also not feasible for household scale implementation. In this aspect, the adsorption techniques are economical and can be applied in household scale, even in low income groups. Many adsorbent materials such as resins, sediment, sludge, bentonite, alumina, silica gel, waste tyre rubber, zeolites, sand, activated carbons, etc. have been investigated for the adsorption of AS. However, Pollard *et al.*³ have suggested that adsorbents are referred to be low-cost, when they are abundant and need little processing, either they are present in nature or as a derivative, or obtained as a waste product from another industry. In this study, we have procured a low-cost, readily abundant and environment-friendly over-burnt brick waste as an adsorbent, and we also propose its treatment with nitric acid, sodium hydroxide and ferric chloride solutions to modulate its physico-chemical properties to achieve maximum AS removal efficiency. These immense and weighty constituents of over-burnt brick wastes might be employed in limited construction applications; otherwise, they are mainly subjected to dumping into the landfill areas through an expensive practice. Thus, these materials might be an alternative adsorbent for treating the AS bearing effluents. To the best of our knowledge, these over-burnt brick materials have not been employed so far for the removal of AS from the aqueous environment.

II. Materials and methods

A. Reagents and instruments

Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), acridine orange (ACO), glacial acetic acid, toluene were procured from BDH (AR grade). All chemicals used in this study were of high purity and were used without further purification. Double distilled water was used throughout the entire study.

Double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (SPECTRASCAN UV 2600, Chemito, India) was used for measuring the absorbance readings. A high precision electronic balance (Afcoset, India) was used

for weighing purpose. Digital pH meter (DHP-500, SICO, India) was used for pH measurements. SEM and EDAX analyses were performed in a scanning electron microscope (JEOL JSM5800, Japan).

B. Preparation of sorbent

The over-burnt brick waste was obtained from local brick manufacturer situated near Kharagpur, and it was washed thoroughly with distilled water. After that, the material was dried in hot air oven at temperature of 105°C for 24 h. The dried sample was then crushed manually using a hammer and ground with an iron pestle before being screened with IS sieves to obtain five different size fractions such as 1.18, 0.6, 0.3, 0.075 and 0.045 mm. The mass retained on the above fractions were collected and moistened with distilled water and kept in a muffle furnace at pre-heated conditions of 600°C for 2 h to enhance its porosity. Both the samples (i.e. pre-heated and post-heated) were used without any further treatment.

In addition to this, the raw brick granules with 0.075–0.3 mm size were treated with HNO₃, NaOH and FeCl₃ solution. The modification was done as follows : 5 g of brick granules were stirred with 50 mL of 1 N HNO₃ at room temperature for overnight. The assortment of the size fraction of brick granules having diameter in between 0.075–0.3 mm was based on our preliminary adsorption experiments for SDS removal.

Thereafter, the solids were collected by filtration, washed with distilled water several times in order to attain neutral pH and dried first at 105°C for overnight in the oven and then finally at 600°C for 2 h in the muffle furnace. The same procedure was applied on brick granules with 1 N NaOH and 1% FeCl₃ solution also. The brick granules treated with 1 N HNO₃, 1 N NaOH and 1% FeCl₃ were designated as BG-3, BG-4 and BG-5, respectively. The detailed steps for adsorbent preparation are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Steps for adsorbent preparation.

C. Analytical method

The concentration of SDS present in the water sample was determined by the spectrophotometric method described earlier⁴. In this method, 10 mL each of the diluted samples (in the range of 0.1–6.0 mg/L of SDS) was transferred in to a 25 mL separating funnel along with 100 μ L of glacial acetic acid and 100 μ L of 5×10^{-3} M solution of ACO. Then, 5 mL of toluene was mixed with it and shaken for 1 min. After that, the mixture was allowed to settle for 5 min until the toluene layer separated from the aqueous layer. The aqueous layer was discarded and the absorbance of the toluene layer was measured at 467 nm. The noted absorbance was plotted against the concentration of SDS to prepare the calibration curve.

D. Experimental studies

The batch adsorption studies were performed in 100 mL Erlenmeyer flask by transferring 30 mL of required SDS solution into the weighed brick granules and the pH of the solution was monitored at neutral. The flasks were tightly stoppered and the solution was agitated in the BOD incubator-shaker for 6 h at 30°C and at 150 rpm, in order to accomplish equilibrium prior to filtration. All adsorption experiments were carried out in duplicate and the

average values were considered for further calculations. The influence of initial pH of the SDS solution during the adsorption process was demonstrated by adding either 0.1 N NaOH or HCl. To determine the equilibrium time, the kinetic studies were performed at an interval of 30 min. The adsorption performance was examined by calculating the percentage removal efficiency and the SDS concentration in the sorbent phase.

III. Results and discussion

A. Comparison of adsorption performance of untreated and treated brick granules

Preliminary adsorption studies on SDS removal were performed to examine the effect of size fraction of the brick granules. Results showed that brick granules having size range of 0.075–0.3 mm were the best (Fig. 2). In a typical experiment, 30 mL SDS solution (conc. 100 mg/L) at 30°C was shaken for 6 h at 150 rpm. The adsorbent dose was selected as 5 and 10 g/L. In addition, all of the post-heated brick granules showed higher SDS removal compared to pre-heated samples due to the enhanced porosity; and the data reveal that the post-heated brick granules having size range 0.075–0.3 mm (i.e. BG-2) showed the maximum removal efficacy (51.44%) (Fig. 2). Similar studies were carried with three other types of chemically treated brick granules viz. BG-3, BG-4 and BG-5 to see their effects on the adsorp-

Fig. 2. Effect of size of brick granules on the removal of SDS (SDS concentration = 100 mg/L, contact time = 6 h, temperature = 30°C, pH = ~6.5).

tion of SDS. It has been found that, among these three adsorbents, the maximum percentage removal was exhibited by BG-5 (Fig. 3). Again when compared with BG-1 and BG-2, BG-5 showed still higher removal of SDS. Thus, here BG-5 was considered for further adsorption studies.

Fig. 3. Performance of modified brick granules on the removal of SDS (adsorbent dose = 10 g/L, SDS concentration = 100 mg/L, contact time = 6 h, temperature = 30°C, pH = ~6.5).

The SEM images of BG-5 (Fig. 4) indicated the presence of noticeable pores, which might cause an increase in the surface area and pore volumes of the modulated brick granules after treatment with FeCl₃

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of the FeCl₃ treated bricks (BG-5).

solution. The EDAX analysis of BG-5 indicated the presence of silicon, oxygen and a small percentage of iron, sodium, magnesium, aluminum, potassium and titanium (Table 1). The presence of metals in the oxide form in brick may lead to the effective removal of SDS.

Table 1. EDAX analysis for BG-5

Element	Weight%	Atomic%
O	47.01	61.82
Si	31.71	23.75
Al	12.32	9.60
Fe	3.22	1.21
K	2.65	1.43
Ti	1.05	0.46
Mg	0.91	0.78
Na	0.83	0.76
Cl	0.29	0.17

B. Effect of adsorption parameters on the SDS removal

The initial pH of the SDS solution is a significant operational parameter for the adsorption process. Fig. 5 exhibits the relationship between the pH and percentage removal of SDS across a pH range of 2.0–11.0. The initial SDS concentration was fixed at 100 mg/L. The maximum percentage removal was accomplished under acidic conditions. The reason is that, the pH_{ZPC} of BG-5 was 6.18 as shown in the inset of Fig. 5. So, at solution pH > 6.18, the surface of the material became negatively charged leading to reduced adsorption of anionic surfactant (AS). The zero point charge (pH_{ZPC}) of the adsorbent was examined by the procedure reported earlier⁵. The reduced adsorption at alkaline pH was possibly due to the competition between the hydroxide ions and the anionic SDS groups.

Fig. 5. Effect of initial pH on SDS removal by BG-5 (SDS concentration = 100 mg/L, BG-5 dosage = 10 g/L, contact time = 6 h, temperature = 30°C).

The effect of adsorbent dose on the SDS removal by BG-5 is presented in Fig. 6. It was observed from the experimental data that, the removal efficacy increased from 17.86 to 81.54% with an increase in adsorbent dosage from 0.5 to 10.0 g/L. This value remained unchanged when the dose of BG-5 was higher than 10 g/L. As the concentration of SDS was fixed at 100 mg/L, by increasing the dose of BG-5, the surface area for the adsorption was increased.

Fig. 6. Effect of adsorbent dose on the removal of SDS using BG-5 (SDS concentration = 100 mg/L, pH = ~6.5, contact time = 6 h, temperature = 30°C).

The influence of SDS concentration on the adsorption was also examined. Here, the adsorbent dose was fixed at 10 g/L, pH at ~6.5, and the contact time at 6 h. Initial SDS concentration was varied from 10 to 400 mg/L. SDS removal efficacy decreased with the increment of SDS concentration, and the maximum percentage of removal was observed at lower concentrations 10–40 mg/L (Fig. 7), although the amount of SDS per unit mass of brick

Fig. 7. Effect of the initial SDS concentration on SDS removal by BG-5 (adsorbent dose = 10 g/L, pH = ~6.5, contact time = 6 h, temperature = 30°C).

adsorbent increased with an increase in the SDS concentrations from 10 to 400 mg/L.

The amount of SDS removed at different contact times is presented in Fig. 8. The dose of BG-5 granules was 10 g/L, and the initial SDS concentration was 100 mg/L. In the first 6 h, the amount of SDS uptake increased, as the contact time increased, but afterwards it gradually came to a constant value, signifying accomplishment of equilibrium. In addition, it was noted that up to 75–80% of the total SDS uptake could be achieved in the initial 6 h, which was due to the presence of more vacant sites in the early stage. However, as time proceeded, the relative number of adsorption sites diminished, leading to a decrease in the sorption rates during 6–10 h.

Fig. 8. Progress of SDS removal over time using BG-5 as adsorbent (SDS concentration = 100 mg/L, adsorbent dose = 10 g/L, pH = ~6.5).

C. Kinetics of adsorption

In this study, pseudo-first and pseudo-second order kinetic models have been investigated. The pseudo-first order⁶ and pseudo-second order⁷ models can be expressed by eqs. (1) and (2), respectively,

$$\ln(q_e - q_t) = \ln q_e - k_1 t \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \left(\frac{1}{q_e}\right)t \quad (2)$$

where q_e and q_t are the amount of SDS sorbed (in mg/g) at equilibrium and at time t respectively, k_1 is the pseudo-first order rate constant in $1/h$ and k_2 is the pseudo-second order rate constant in $g/(mg \cdot h)$.

The experimental and non-linear theoretical kinetic plots (Fig. 9) indicate that, the present adsorption of SDS on BG-5 follow pseudo-second order kinetic model better than the pseudo-first order model. Additionally, the determination coefficient R^2 (0.9952) explores that the pseudo-second order model fits better to the experimental data (Table 2). As shown in Table 2, the experimental q_e ($q_{e,exp}$) and theoretical q_e ($q_{e,cal}$) values are also in a better agreement for pseudo-second order kinetic model. The values of kinetic parameters for SDS sorption on to BG-5 are compiled in Table 2. These results suggest that, the removal process is caused by chemisorption.

Fig. 9. Experimental and non-linear theoretical kinetic plots of adsorption of SDS on BG-5.

D. Isothermal modeling

To examine the adsorption capacity of BG-5 for the removal of SDS, the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models were examined. The linearized form of the Langmuir⁸ and Freundlich⁹ isotherms are expressed by eqs. (3) and (4), respectively,

$$\frac{C_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{K_L q_{max}} + \frac{C_e}{q_{max}} \quad (3)$$

$$\ln q_e = \ln K_F + \frac{1}{n} \ln C_e \quad (4)$$

where K_L is the Langmuir constant which is related to the binding energy or the affinity parameter of the adsorption process, q_{max} is the maximum adsorption capacity (mg/g), C_e is the concentration of SDS at equilibrium (mg/L), q_e is the amount of the SDS adsorbed per unit mass of the adsorbent at equilibrium (mg/g). In Freundlich isotherm, K_F and n indicates the adsorption capacity and adsorption intensity, respectively. The determination coefficients R^2 obtained from both the isotherm models are given in Table 3. When comparing the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms, the experimental data fitted

Table 2. Comparison of adsorption kinetic parameters

Model	$q_{e,exp}$ (mg/g)	Estimated linearized equation	R^2
Pseudo-first order	8.39	$\ln (q_e - q_t) = -0.5315 t + 1.8017$ $k_1 = 0.5315 \text{ h}^{-1}$ $q_{e,cal} = 6.06 \text{ mg/g}$	0.9804
Pseudo-second order	8.39	$t/q_t = 0.0992 t + 0.1824$ $k_2 = 0.0539 \text{ g/(mg h)}$ $q_{e,cal} = 10.08 \text{ mg/g}$ $h = 5.4766 \text{ mg/(g h)}$	0.9952

Table 3. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm constants for the removal of SDS by BG-5

Model	$q_{e,exp}$ (mg/g)	Estimated linearized equation	R^2
Langmuir	14.99	$C_e/q_e = 0.0686 C_e + 0.8084$ $q_m = 14.58 \text{ mg/g}$ $K_L = 0.0848 \text{ L/mg}$	0.9875
Freundlich	14.99	$\ln q_e = 0.2811 \ln C_e + 1.2025$ $1/n = 0.2811$ $K_F = 3.3284$	0.9945

well with the Freundlich equation. Additionally, the experimental non-linear curve is in good agreement with the Freundlich isotherm (Fig. 10). The value of $1/n$ (0.2811) indicates that, the adsorption is favourable¹⁰.

Fig. 10. Experimental and theoretical adsorption isotherms for SDS removal by BG-5.

(J/K/mol), ΔH the enthalpy change (kJ/mol), ΔG the Gibb's free energy change (kJ/mol) for the adsorption system, R the universal gas constant (8.314 J mol//K) and T the temperature (K). The ΔS , ΔH and ΔG values acquired are shown in Table 4. The experiments were performed at 10°C, 30°C and 50°C. The equilibrium time was 6 h. Initial concentrations of SDS were selected as 50 and 100 mg/L.

At all temperatures studied, negative values of ΔG were obtained, which confirmed the spontaneity and feasibility of the adsorption of SDS on BG-5 adsorbent. The negative ΔH values indicate that, the adsorption is exothermic, and the values of ΔS represent the change in the randomness at the adsorbent-adsorbate interface during the adsorption process. The above observations revealed that the adsorption of SDS on BG-5 granules decreased when

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of SDS on to BG-5

C_0 (mg/L)	Temperature (°C)	ΔG (kJ/mol)	ΔH (kJ/mol)	ΔS (J/K/mol)	R^2
50	10	-7.521	-22.735	-53.939	0.9955
	30	-6.275			
	50	-5.379			
100	10	-4.277	-10.949	-23.565	0.9999
	30	-3.815			
	50	-3.334			

E. Adsorption thermodynamics

Thermodynamic study was carried out to examine the effect of temperature on the percentage removal of SDS by BG-5. The free energy change (ΔG), enthalpy change (ΔH) and entropy change (ΔS) were calculated using the eqs. (5)–(7)¹⁰,

$$K_e = \frac{C_0 - C_e}{C_e} \quad (5)$$

$$\ln K_e = \left(\frac{\Delta S}{R} \right) - \left(\frac{\Delta H}{RT} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_e \quad (7)$$

where C_0 and C_e are the initial and equilibrium SDS concentration (mg/L), K_e the equilibrium constant (or distribution coefficient), ΔS the entropy change

the temperature was increased from 10 to 50°C, indicating that the process was exothermic¹¹.

IV. Conclusion

A low-cost treatment process has been proposed for the removal of anionic surfactant (e.g. SDS) through adsorption on 1% FeCl₃ treated over-burnt brick waste. The material was designated as BG-5. The detailed batch mode adsorption studies were carried out. Maximum adsorption was observed under the acidic conditions and it gradually decreased to minimal at pH 10. The pH_{ZPC} of BG-5 was 6.18. So, at solution pH > 6.18, the surface of the material became negative leading to reduced adsorption of negatively charged surfactant. The removal efficiency decreased on increasing initial SDS concen-

tration. The optimum adsorbent dose and equilibrium time were found to be 10 g/L and 6 h, respectively. Isotherm data showed better fit to Freundlich model compared to Langmuir model. The kinetic studies showed that, the adsorption followed pseudo-second order model. The adsorption was facilitated at lower temperature. Results suggested that the adsorption of SDS was exothermic and spontaneous in nature.

References

1. V. K. Whiting, G. M. Cripe and J. E. Lepo, *Arch. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 1996, **31**, 293.
2. K. Holmberg, B. Jonsson, B. Kronberg and B. Lindman, "Surfactants and Polymers in Aqueous Solution", Wiley, 2nd ed., Chichester, England, 2003.
3. S. J. T. Pollard, G. D. Fowler, C. J. Sollars and R. Perry, *Sci. Total Environ.*, 1992, **116**, 31.
4. A. Adak, M. Bandyopadhyay and A. Pal, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 2005, **12**, 145.
5. S. Saha and A. Pal, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, 2014, **134**, 26.
6. S. Lagergren, *K. Sven. Vetenskapsakad. Handl.*, 1898, **24**, 1.
7. Y. S. Ho and G. Mckay, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 1998, **70**, 115.
8. I. Langmuir, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 2221.
9. H. M. F. Freundlich, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1906, **57**, 385.
10. M. U. Khobragade and A. Pal, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.*, 2014, **2**, 2295.
11. S. K. Maji, A. Pal, T. Pal and A. Adak, *J. Surf. Sci. Technol.*, 2007, **23**, 161.